

LRP-Enhanced LSTM Model for Interpretable Prediction of Parkinson's Disease Progression

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ABSTRACT

This study develops an interpretable deep learning model to identify key factors influencing Parkinson's disease progression. Using data from patients with parkinsonian symptoms (including PD, atypical, and vascular parkinsonism) undergoing chronic levodopa therapy, monitored through LD TM from January 14, 2015, to December 30, 2020, with Ethics Committee approval (CE 137-2021-OSS-AUSLBO), we applied an LSTM-based neural network. The model integrates clinical, pharmacokinetic, and pharmacodynamic data to predict therapeutic responses to levodopa, while Layer-wise Relevance Propagation (LRP) provides interpretability by highlighting critical features driving treatment outcomes. MDS-UPDRS Part III emerged as the most influential feature, strongly associated with motor symptom severity, followed by therapeutic response dynamics, including dyskinesias and the MP phase, as well as clinical markers such as the HY score, drug-drug interactions (DDI), and levodopa dose per kg. Pharmacokinetic variables, especially DDI, AUC, and Cmax, showed high relevance scores, indicating their significant role in predicting PD outcomes. The heatmap of relevance scores further revealed that LD Pharmacodynamics was the most impactful factor (0.47), followed by LD Pharmacokinetics (0.31) and Patient Characteristics (0.22). These findings underscore the importance of dynamic drug responses in forecasting disease progression, thereby enhancing personalized PD care through interpretable machine learning.

1. Introduction

Among 100 Parkinson's patients who began levodopa treatment before 1968, 47 were still on the drug after five years, with half showing at least a 25% improvement from their baseline condition. Although initial functional ratings improved significantly within the first two years, they gradually declined toward pretreatment levels over time. Key side effects included involuntary movements, motor fluctuations, balance issues, and dementia, while 32 of the original patients had died. Mortality rates were 1.9 times higher than the general U.S. population — still lower than the pre-levodopa era rate of 2.9. Despite not being a cure, levodopa remains the most effective long-term treatment for managing Parkinson's symptoms [1].

Accurate early differentiation between Parkinson's disease and atypical parkinsonisms (APs) remains challenging due to overlapping symptoms. Levodopa (LD) responsiveness is a key diagnostic feature of PD, but traditional clinical assessments lack objectivity. A study from the BoProPark cohort evaluated a subacute low-dose LD kinetic-dynamic test using the area under the effect-time curve of tapping speed as a quantitative biomarker. The test was applied at baseline in 100 patients with parkinsonian signs within three years of motor onset, later diagnosed as PD or APs. Area under the effect-time curve of tapping speed values were similar in PD subgroups but significantly reduced in APs

($p < 0.001$). These findings support area under the effect-time curve of tapping speed values as a reliable, objective tool for assessing LD motor response, enhancing early diagnostic accuracy between PD and APs [2]. In [3] Personalized therapy in Parkinson's disease (PD) aims to manage motor and non-motor symptoms through ongoing adjustment of dopamine-substituting drugs, particularly levodopa. Therapeutic drug monitoring (TDM) may optimize treatment, as levodopa's short half-life, variable gastric emptying, and amino acid competition affect its plasma levels. Poor drug response may stem from non-compliance or interactions with medications for comorbid conditions. Measuring plasma levels of levodopa and other PD drugs (e.g., dopamine agonists, COMT and MAO-B inhibitors) could improve dosing accuracy. TDM may enhance treatment efficacy, reduce side effects, and support precision medicine, highlighting the need for dedicated clinical studies.

Continuous levodopa sensing as in [4] could improve Parkinson's disease management by optimizing titration and treatment efficacy, yet its development is limited by the lack of specific molecular recognition elements and uncertain clinical utility. This review examines current levodopa sensing methods and their limitations, including metabolic interference, adjunct medications, and temporal resolution. It highlights a proposed interferent panel for sensor validation and offers a comparative analysis of molecular recognition elements, outlining their respective strengths and limitations. In [5] Levodopa equivalent dose (LED) conversion

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formulae enable comparison of antiparkinsonian drug regimens across clinical trials in Parkinson's disease. The widely used 2010 formulae by Tomlinson et al. are now outdated due to the introduction of new drugs and formulations. Updated consensus-based LED conversions are essential for accurate cross-study comparisons. This Position Paper presents revised LED values to support consistent evaluation of pharmacological, surgical, and non-pharmacological interventions in PD research.

A prediction model as in [6] for acute orthostatic hypotension post-levodopa (AOHPL) in Parkinson's disease was developed and validated using data from 374 patients. The Random Forest model showed the best performance (AUC 0.776, accuracy 73.6%), with key predictors being pre-medication systolic and diastolic blood pressure drops. The model achieved 72% accuracy on independent test data. This tool may assist clinicians in identifying patients at risk of AOHPL, supporting personalized treatment and improving patient safety and quality of life. Artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML) have emerged as powerful tools for PD diagnosis, prediction, and treatment. This review highlights their applications in identifying biomarkers, analyzing speech, gait, handwriting, and neuroimaging data. It also explores AI's role in lipidomics, gut-brain interactions, neurosurgery, drug discovery, and integrating digital health technologies for improved PD management [7]. In [8], a novel explainable AI method called LRP-based approximate linear weights (ALW), which simplifies the neural network's function into a 2D kernel achieving 73% classification accuracy and revealing differentiating tremor frequency features (3–30 Hz) through STFT preprocessing, aligning with medical knowledge while uncovering new insights into frequency bands and body parts. A novel LSTM-based deep learning architecture that eliminates manual feature engineering and effectively captures long-term temporal dependencies in gait patterns to detect freezing of gait (FOG) episodes in Parkinson's disease patients, utilizing dropout, L2 regularization, and the Adam optimizer to achieve state-of-the-art performance with 97.71% accuracy, 99% sensitivity, 98% precision, and 96% specificity explained in [9].

This study focuses on developing an interpretable deep learning model to identify key factors involved in Parkinson's disease progression. We analyzed data from patients with parkinsonian symptoms (PD, atypical, or vascular) receiving chronic levodopa therapy, monitored through LD TM from January 14, 2015, to December 30, 2020, with Ethics Committee approval (CE 137-2021-OSS-AUSLBO). The LD TM procedure involved a 12-hour medication washout, administration of a standardized LD dose, serial venous blood sampling for plasma levodopa concentration analysis, motor function testing, and comprehensive clinical assessments. An LSTM-based neural network was used to predict therapeutic response to levodopa by incorporating clinical, pharmacokinetic, and pharmacodynamic variables. To ensure interpretability, LRP was applied, revealing the most critical features influencing individual treatment outcomes.

2. Materials and Methods

Patients: This retrospective study analyzed prospectively collected data from patients with parkinsonian symptoms (including PD, atypical parkinsonisms, or vascular parkinsonism) receiving chronic levodopa therapy and monitored through LD TM between January 14, 2015, and December 30, 2020, with Ethics Committee approval (CE 137-2021-OSS-AUSLBO) and no requirement for informed consent [10]. Inclusion criteria were chronic levodopa therapy for at least 3 months using standard-release LD/DCI (benserazide or carbidopa) at a 4:1 ratio, with no dosage changes of LD or other antiparkinsonian drugs in the previous week. Exclusion criteria included LD-naïve subjects, use of LD/CD at a 10:1 ratio or extended-release formulations, concurrent COMT inhibitors, enteral LD/CD gel therapy, or detectable plasma LD levels at baseline (T0).

Monitoring protocol for levodopa pharmacokinetics and pharmacodynamics: The LD TM protocol involved overnight fasting and a 12-hour washout, followed by administration of the patient's regular morning dose of LD/BZ or LD/CD with 100 mL water, and collection of venous blood samples at specified intervals for LD plasma concentration analysis using HPLC with coulometric detection. Motor responses were evaluated via finger tapping [11], TUG, and CDRS for dyskinesias [12], along with clinical assessments (Hoehn Yahr, MDS-UPDRS III) [13], vital signs in different postures, and a standardized breakfast given 75–90 minutes post-dose. Demographic, clinical, therapeutic, and lifestyle data were recorded, LD equivalent daily dose calculated per Schade et al., and a suspected clinical diagnosis noted if a definitive one was unavailable at the time of testing.

3. Proposed System

This study aims to identify key factors influencing the clinical pharmacokinetics and pharmacodynamics of Levodopa using LRP. The system is designed to predict dominant contributors to Parkinson's disease progression by analyzing patient characteristics, Levodopa kinetic and dynamic variables, medication profiles, and lifestyle factors. LRP is implemented within LSTM neural network architectures to evaluate the model's effectiveness in identifying critical contributors to the onset and progression of Parkinson's disease. The dataset used for prediction is from [10]. It includes the following features:

Patient characteristics – Sex, age, weight, height, BMI, test dose, test dose per kg, daily dose, and formulation.

Levodopa (LD) pharmacokinetic – DDI (drug-drug Interaction), C_{max} (maximum plasma concentration), multiple peaks, T_{max} (time to reach C_{max}), and AUC (area under the plasma concentration-time curve).

Levodopa (LD) pharmacodynamic – Response start time (in minutes), ON state at 180 minutes, drug distribution profile, duration of the motor performance (MP) phase, duration of therapeutic effect, presence of dyskinesias, dystonias,

dystonia score, MDS-UPDRS Part III, UPDRS score and HY scale.

We predict the therapeutic response to Levodopa in Parkinson's disease patients by analyzing key features using neural network architecture LSTM. The predictions focus on identifying patient-specific responses based on clinical, pharmacokinetic, and pharmacodynamic data. To interpret the model's decisions, we apply an enhanced LRP, which provides insights into the most influential factors contributing to treatment outcomes.

3.1. LSTM

LSTM networks, a specialized type of recurrent neural network (RNN), are particularly effective in modeling the temporal dynamics of Parkinson's disease (PD) progression. Introduced by Hochreiter Schmidhuber (1997) [14], LSTMs address the vanishing gradient problem in traditional RNNs through their gated mechanisms, enabling robust learning of long-term dependencies in sequential clinical data. This capability makes them well-suited for predicting PD progression, where disease severity evolves over time based on factors such as motor symptoms (e.g., UPDRS scores), medication regimens (e.g., levodopa dosing), and non-motor indicators (e.g., cognitive decline) [15].

3.1.1. LSTM Architecture and Gated Computation

LSTM networks maintain and update two internal states: the hidden state h_t and the cell state C_t . These are controlled through a series of gates—forget, input, and output—that regulate information flow at each time step t . The LSTM processes the current input x_t and the previous hidden state h_{t-1} to compute the current states. Below are the key operations and detailed explanations of each term:

$$f_t = \sigma(W_f[h_{t-1}, x_t] + b_f) \quad (1)$$

Where, f_t : Forget gate vector at time step t . It determines how much of the previous cell state C_{t-1} should be retained. σ : Sigmoid activation function that maps values to the range (0, 1), controlling the degree of forgetting. W_f : Weight matrix associated with the forget gate. $[h_{t-1}, x_t]$: Concatenation of the previous hidden state h_{t-1} and the current input x_t . b_f : Bias vector for the forget gate.

$$i_t = \sigma(W_i[h_{t-1}, x_t] + b_i) \quad (2)$$

Where, i_t : Input gate vector at time step t . It controls how much of the new candidate cell state should be added to the memory. W_i : Weight matrix for the input gate. b_i : Bias vector for the input gate.

$$C_t = f_t \odot C_{t-1} + i_t \odot \tanh(W_C[h_{t-1}, x_t] + b_C) \quad (3)$$

Where, C_t : Updated cell state at time t , serving as the memory of the LSTM. $f_t \odot C_{t-1}$: Element-wise product (\odot) representing the retained portion of the previous cell state. $i_t \odot \tanh(W_C[h_{t-1}, x_t] + b_C)$: New candidate memory content to be added, gated by i_t . W_C : Weight matrix for computing the candidate cell state. b_C : Bias vector for the candidate cell

state. \tanh : Hyperbolic tangent function that squashes values between -1 and 1 , used for candidate state generation.

$$h_t = o_t \odot \tanh(C_t) \quad (4)$$

Where, h_t : Hidden state (also the output of the LSTM unit) at time step t . o_t : Output gate vector, computed similarly (usually $o_t = \sigma(W_o[h_{t-1}, x_t] + b_o)$). $\tanh(C_t)$: Non-linear transformation of the updated cell state. \odot : Element-wise multiplication, used to filter the memory content through the output gate.

3.2. LRP for LSTM in Parkinson's Disease Progression

Predicting Parkinson's disease progression is crucial for personalized treatment. LSTM networks have shown potential in modeling PD using clinical data, such as motor scores and medication doses. However, LSTMs are often considered black-box models, limiting clinical application due to a lack of interpretability. LRP addresses this by providing explanations for the model's predictions, assigning relevance scores to input features. LRP helps identify key factors influencing disease progression, enhancing decision-making and clinical trust in LSTM models. Adapting LRP to LSTMs improves transparency, enabling better integration of machine learning in personalized PD care.

3.2.1. LRP through the LSTM architecture

The LSTM architecture processes sequential data through a series of interconnected gates (input, forget, and output) and memory cells, which selectively retain, update, and propagate information across time steps. To apply LRP, we decompose the LSTM's predictions by backpropagating relevance through these gating mechanisms and hidden states, assigning importance scores to input features while preserving the temporal dependencies learned by the model. Output to Hidden State is:

$$R_{h_t} = \frac{h_t \odot (W_{hy}^T R_y)}{\sum_k h_k W_{hy}^T + \epsilon} \quad (5)$$

Where, R_{h_t} : Relevance score assigned to the hidden state h_t at time t . h_t : The hidden state vector at time t . W_{hy} : Weight matrix between the hidden state h_t and the output layer y . R_y : Relevance score of the model's output. \odot : Element-wise multiplication (Hadamard product). $\sum_k h_k W_{hy}^T$: Sum over all hidden units to normalize the relevance. ϵ : A small constant added for numerical stability.

Cell State Decomposition:

$$R_{C_t} = \left(\frac{f_t \odot C_{t-1}}{C_t + \epsilon} \right)_F \odot R_{h_t} + \left(\frac{i_t \odot \tilde{C}_t}{C_t + \epsilon} \right)_I \odot R_{h_t} \quad (6)$$

Where, R_{C_t} : Relevance score assigned to the cell state C_t . (f_t : Forget gate activation at time t . C_{t-1} : Previous cell state. C_t : Current cell state. i_t : Input gate activation at time t . \tilde{C}_t : Candidate cell state. R_{h_t} : Relevance score of the hidden state

Figure 1: LRP-based relevance scores for PD progression prediction

h_t . ϵ : A small constant added for numerical stability.
Input Attribution, For feature dimension d at time t :

$$R_{x_t^{(d)}} = \sum_{g \in \{f, i, o\}} \frac{x_t^{(d)} W_{gx}^{(d)}}{g_t + \epsilon} \odot R_{g_t} \quad (7)$$

Where, $R_{x_t^{(d)}}$: Relevance score assigned to the d -th feature of the input x_t at time t . $x_t^{(d)}$: The d -th feature of the input vector x_t . $W_{gx}^{(d)}$: Weight matrix element between the d -th input feature and the gate activation for gate $g \in \{f, i, o\}$. g_t : Gate activation (forget f_t , input i_t , or output o_t) at time t . R_{g_t} : Relevance score for the gate g_t . ϵ : A small constant added for numerical stability.

4. Results

After applying an LSTM model and interpreting its predictions using LRP, the most prominent factors associated with Parkinson's disease progression are identified based on their contribution to the model's output relevance scores. These highlight which features most influence the model's prediction of disease worsening.

4.1. Feature contributing to Parkinson's disease progression

Figure. 1 presents a heatmap illustrating the relevance scores of each feature contributing to Parkinson's disease progression prediction, as interpreted by the LSTM model using LRP. The x-axis shows the clinical and pharmacological features, and the y-axis shows their normalized relevance scores (ranging from 0 to 1), where higher scores indicate greater influence on the model's decision. The justification for this ordering is:

- **MDS-UPDRS Part III Score (0.92)**

This is the gold standard clinical tool for assessing

motor symptom severity [16]. It directly quantifies tremor, rigidity, and bradykinesia, which are core to diagnosing and tracking PD progression. Its consistently high relevance score from LRP reflects its dominant predictive power and clinical validity.

- **Duration of Therapeutic Effect (0.85)**

As PD advances, the response to levodopa shortens, leading to wearing-off episodes. Duration of therapeutic effect serves as a dynamic marker for treatment efficacy and neurodegeneration pace, justifying its near-top relevance.

- **Dyskinesias Severity (0.81)**

Dyskinesias typically emerge after long-term levodopa use and are exacerbated by disease progression. Their presence suggests advanced motor complications and treatment side effects, which align with reduced dopaminergic reserve and fluctuating responses.

- **Motor Performance (MP) Phase Duration (0.77)**

A shorter or unstable MP phase signals increased motor fluctuations, reduced drug efficacy, and worsening control over voluntary movement. It encapsulates subtle patterns of instability not always captured by clinical scores.

- **H&Y Stage (0.73)**

The Hoehn & Yahr scale stages [17] axial and postural impairments, which typically worsen in mid to late PD. While less granular than MDS-UPDRS, it offers a useful snapshot of overall disease stage and complements motor phase metrics.

Figure 2: PK variables associated with Parkinson's disease progression

- **Dose-Dose Interval (DDI) (0.65)**

A need for more frequent dosing reflects shorter response durations and greater motor fluctuation, especially in moderate to severe PD. DDI reflects compensatory treatment strategies adopted as disease resistance builds.

- **Levodopa Dose per kg (0.62)**

Higher weight-adjusted dosages often indicate disease advancement, especially when dose increases no longer yield proportional symptomatic relief. It captures the pharmacological burden and patient-specific dosing response.

MDS-UPDRS Part III emerged as the most relevant feature, underscoring its strong association with motor symptom severity in Parkinson's disease. Additionally, therapeutic response dynamics (such as duration of effect, dyskinesias, and MP phase), along with HY score, drug-drug interactions (DDI), and levodopa dose per kg, were identified as significant contributors, reflecting both clinical and pharmacological markers of disease progression.

4.2. PK variable on Parkinson's disease

The influence of pharmacokinetic (PK) variables on Parkinson's disease progression, determined through LRP applied to an LSTM model is given in Figure. 2. DDI (Drug-Drug Interaction) and AUC (Area Under Curve) show the highest relevance scores (0.65 and 0.61, respectively), suggesting that dosing frequency and total drug exposure are major contributors to predicting Parkinson's disease outcomes. Cmax (Maximum Plasma Concentration) also carries significant weight (0.58), indicating that peak drug levels impact the therapeutic effect and side effects. Multiple Peaks and Tmax (Time to Cmax) have relatively lower scores (0.42 and 0.37), implying a moderate role in influencing disease trajectory or response patterns. These findings highlight how variations in drug absorption and exposure patterns relate to the progression and management of PD symptoms.

4.3. Mean Relevant Score by feature group

The heatmap in Figure. 3 provides a visual representation of the relevance scores for various factors influencing Parkinson's disease progression. LD Pharmacodynamics emerges as the most influential variable, with the highest average relevance score of 0.47, highlighting its significant role in determining patient outcomes. This suggests that dynamic drug responses, such as how the drug interacts with the patient's system, are crucial in predicting the severity and progression of the disease.

Following this, LD Pharmacokinetics ranks second, with a relevance score of 0.31, indicating that how the drug is absorbed, distributed, metabolized, and excreted also plays an important, but somewhat lesser role in predicting outcomes. Lastly, Patient Characteristics, with a score of 0.22, have the lowest relevance, suggesting that while they provide some insight, they are not as predictive as the pharmacokinetic and pharmacodynamic factors in understanding disease progression.

5. Discussion and conclusion

This study demonstrates the potential of an interpretable deep learning approach combining LSTM networks with LRP—to predict Parkinson's disease progression and uncover key contributing factors. Among the analyzed features, motor symptom severity, measured by MDS-UPDRS Part III, emerged as the most relevant, followed by therapeutic response dynamics such as duration of effect, dyskinesias, and MP phase. Clinical and pharmacological markers, including the HY score, drug-drug interactions (DDI), and levodopa dose per kilogram, also significantly contributed to model predictions. Notably, pharmacokinetic variables like dosing frequency (AUC) and peak drug concentration (Cmax) showed the highest relevance scores, emphasizing their strong influence on treatment outcomes. The relevance heatmap further highlighted LD pharmacodynamics as the most impactful factor, whereas patient characteristics had

Figure 3: Mean relevance scores of PK variables in PD progression

lower predictive value—underscoring the primacy of dynamic drug response metrics in disease progression modeling.

Overall, this interpretable LSTM-based framework enhances transparency, supporting its integration into personalized PD care and enabling more informed clinical decision-making. As future work, alternative neural architectures such as MLP, RNN, and GRU may be explored and compared with LSTM to assess performance and interpretability across diverse modeling strategies.

Conflict of Interests

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interests.

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